

ProCleanLakes

Readme file

**20241130-ProCleanLakes-Data
Management Plan-V01**

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Reason(s) for data analysis: *The Data Management Plan (DMP) was created for an effective data management in the project ProCleanLakes*

Creation date of file(s): *11/2024*

Used method(s): *collection of data types and sizes from consortium partners*

Used software (incl. version and add-ons) and tools: N/A

Data: N/A

Code: N/A

Additional files: N/A

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Notes: N/A